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Annotatsiya: *The accounting policy of business entities should follow specific principles. The first standard of the National Accounting Standards of the Republic of Uzbekistan (BHMS) lists the following as the principles of accounting and financial reporting:*

- *accounting with the method of double-sided recording;*
 - *continuity;*
 - *assessment of economic problems, assets and liabilities;*
 - *reliability;*
 - *caution;*
 - *the superiority of content over form;*
 - *comparability of indicators;*
 - *neutrality of financial reporting;*
 - *real value of assets and liabilities;*
 - *compatibility of income and expenses of the reporting period;*
 - *comprehensibility;*
 - *significance;*
 - *importance;*
 - *truthful and unbiased presentation;*
 - *termination;*
 - *consistency;*
 - *timeliness;*
 - *offsetting (mutual coverage of substances);*
- impartiality.*

Key words: *Account system, quick account, statistical account, accounting, units of measure, unit of measure in kind, unit of measure of time, unit of measure of money, requirements for economic accounting, principles of accounting, education supply process, production process, sales process, subject of accounting, business funds, sources of funds, business processes, documentation, inventory, system of accounts, double entry, evaluation, calculation, report*

Kalit soʻzlar: *Hisob tizimi, tezkor hisob, statistik hisob, buxgalteriya hisobi, oʻlchov birliklari, naturadagi oʻlchov birligi, vaqt oʻlchov birligi, pul oʻlchov birligi, xoʻjalik hisobiga qoʻyiladigan talablar, buxgalteriya hisobi tamoyillari, taʼlim jarayoni, ishlab chiqarish jarayoni, sotish. jarayon, buxgalteriya hisobi predmeti, xoʻjalik fondlari, mablagʻlar manbalari, xoʻjalik jarayonlari, hujjatlar, inventarizatsiya, hisoblar tizimi, ikkilamchi yozuv, baholash, hisoblash, hisobot*

The creation of an account is directly related to the creation of a personal society. According to historical data, accounts were used during the primitive community system. In order to save his tribe, the head of the tribe made calculations such as when the season will come, how many people there are in the tribe, and how much food should be collected for them. Initially, fingers were used as counting instruments (in some cases we still use this custom). Even now, every family that is part of the society has its own accounting book. The living conditions of that family are good if the accounts are well established in the family. It can be seen from this that the account is a vital asset and partner of people.

Glossary:

Continuity. The business entity operates continuously. that is, it is considered a subject that will continue to work in the specified future. It is assumed that he has neither the intention nor the need to terminate his activity or significantly reduce the scope of his activity.

In some cases provided by the standards, the actual price may differ from the purchase price.

Understandability. The information provided in financial reports should be understandable to users.

Significance. Financial information must be relevant to meet the needs of users in their decision-making process and assist them in evaluating operational, financial and business performance.

Seriousness. If the omission or misrepresentation of information affects the economic decisions of users of the information made on the basis of financial statements, it is considered material. The importance of information can be influenced by its essence, as well as its value (seriousness).

Fair and impartial presentation. Financial reports should create a true and unbiased picture of the financial situation of the business entity, the results of operations, and the movement of funds.

Completeness. In order to ensure the reliability of financial reports, information should be presented in a sufficiently complete volume.

Consistency. It is considered that the accounting policy is consistently transferred from one period to another. Users should be able to compare the financial statements of

an entity in different accounting periods to determine the basis of changes in its financial position.

Timely delivery. With an unreasonable delay in reporting information, it loses its economic significance. Timely reporting may require a report before all aspects of a transaction or other event are known, which undermines its credibility. On the other hand, if the report is delayed until all aspects are known, even the most reliable information will not be of much use to users, as they will be forced to make decisions earlier. In order to achieve a balance between relevance and reliability, it is necessary to solve the problem of how best to satisfy the needs of users in making economic decisions.

Accounting, like other disciplines, is subject to requirements, as a result of which its characteristics such as methods, duties and obligations, its role in managing the economy, and its future position are strengthened.

Accounting requirements are as follows:

1. The account should be simple and understandable. The main goal of creating a simple and understandable account is to avoid its complexity and to ensure that the account information can be used by the general public.

2. Schedule of the account. This requirement is closely related to the simplicity requirement mentioned above. Having the necessary information and indicators in the account, it is necessary to reduce the costs of accounting as much as possible.

3. Accuracy and accuracy of the account. The basis of this requirement is the accurate and correct recording of the information obtained as a result of monitoring of economic activities in the documents. It is a violation of the law to present the economic account vaguely and incorrectly for various purposes or due to negligence.

4. It is necessary to carry out accounting work on time, that is, any event related to accounting work must be reflected in time and recorded in documents. When this requirement is fully fulfilled, the management of economic activities will be well established, the deficiencies that have occurred or may occur will be eliminated in time.

5. Unity of account indicators and plan indicators. Enterprises, institutions, organizations, regardless of the form of ownership, prepare current and future plan indicators. On the whole economy and their sectors

6. and national plan indicators are determined. The unity of accounting indicators with the same indicators (at the same time, positive differences) is of great importance. The account provides information on the progress of production, trade, supply, agriculture, construction, household services, transport, etc., and provides an opportunity to monitor and analyze the implementation of the plan. It creates an opportunity to find internal and external factors of economic development.

7. Confidentiality is observed when the accountant maintains accounting records. Acquaintance with the content of accounting registers is allowed with the permission of the administration or in the cases provided for by law.

8. Persons authorized to get acquainted with accounting registers must maintain their confidentiality. Violation of confidentiality is the reason for prosecution in accordance with the law.

CONCLUSION

It should be noted that in the development of a new accounting system that meets international standards and corresponds to the characteristics of the market economy, scientists and practitioners do not blindly approach the innovations created in this field in developed countries. Studying the practices of foreign countries, their deep and comprehensive analysis provides an opportunity to improve the accounting system in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Currently, the following units of measurement are used in the accounting system of our republic:

- unit of measurement in kind;
- time (labor) measurement unit;
- monetary unit.

The natural unit of measurement is widely used in quick calculation, statistical calculation, and analytical calculation of accounting. This unit of measurement is needed for the calculation of one type of items. For example, children's shoes, the number of refrigerators, gas meter, etc. (meter, kg, piece, pair, liter, etc.).

The monetary unit is used to summarize economic processes (operations) and tools in a single measure (money), that is, all funds are expressed in a unit of value. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, soum and diny are accepted as monetary units.

The unit of measurement of time (labor) (month, day, hour, minute, second) is used to determine the labor force, number of workers, working hours, etc., used for the production of some statistical or economic products. In a trading company, it is necessary to determine the working time, working hours, working days, manpower, etc. for the turnover of a certain product. The unit of measurement of time is also important in calculating wages with employees. Time measurement units together with in-kind measurement units indicate labor productivity.

There was a demand for accounts at all levels of human society. Because economic accounting means taking into account the production and distribution of consumer goods, clothing, food, etc., necessary for humanity. The main goal of every society is the production, exchange and distribution of necessary goods. In order to achieve this goal, it is necessary to observe the events and phenomena occurring in the social life of people, to take into account the work items, work tools and work processes available in the society. The same task is performed by the economic account.

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